

Prevalence and Determinants of Self-Monitoring of Blood Glucose among Adults with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus in a Tertiary Hospital in Northwest Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Type 2 Diabetes mellitus is a growing public health problem in Nigeria, associated with high and increasing morbidity and mortality from preventable complications. Self-monitoring of blood glucose is an essential component of diabetes self-care, enabling patients to maintain optimal glycaemic control and prevent complications.

Objective: This study aimed to determine the prevalence of self-monitoring of blood glucose and to identify its sociodemographic and clinical determinants, as well as barriers among adults with Type 2 Diabetes mellitus accessing healthcare at a tertiary hospital in Sokoto, Nigeria.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out among 218 adults with Type II Diabetes mellitus attending the Medical Outpatient Clinic of Usmanu Danfodiyo University Teaching Hospital, Sokoto. Participants were selected using simple random sampling technique, and data were obtained using a pretested, interviewer-administered proforma. Analysis was done using the SPSS Statistics and involved descriptive and inferential statistics, using chi-square tests and logistic regression, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The prevalence of self-monitoring of blood glucose among respondents was 55.5%. Independent predictors included income, employment, duration of illness and having had diabetes health education. The leading barriers were cost of glucometers/test strips (57.7%) and lack of knowledge on glucometer use (48.6%).

Conclusion: The study revealed a moderately high prevalence of self-monitoring of blood glucose among adults with T2DM in Sokoto, influenced by respondents' socioeconomic status, duration of diabetes, and education. High cost and inadequate knowledge remain barriers to self-monitoring of blood glucose.

Keywords: Type 2 Diabetes mellitus, Self-Monitoring of Blood Glucose, Prevalence, Determinants.

Introduction

Diabetes Mellitus (DM) is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by persistent hyperglycaemia resulting from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both. Sustained elevations in blood glucose ultimately lead to damage in multiple organ systems, particularly the nerves and blood vessels.^{1,2} Sub-saharan Africa continues to experience a rapid rise in DM prevalence, with Nigeria accounting for a substantial proportion of the regional burden.³ This increasing prevalence of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) in Nigeria contributes significantly to morbidity, mortality, and escalating healthcare costs, underscoring the urgent need for effective management strategies.⁴ Optimal glycaemic control remains central to preventing both acute and long-term complications of T2DM.⁵ Self-monitoring of blood glucose (SMBG) is a key component of DM self-management. It involves regular measurement and documentation of blood glucose levels by individuals living with diabetes.⁶ Self-monitoring of blood glucose is widely recommended by international guidelines as part of routine care, particularly for patients on insulin therapy and many on oral glucose-lowering agents.⁷ The American Diabetes Association further emphasizes that SMBG should be individualized based on treatment regimen, risk of hypoglycaemia, and the patient's capacity to use the results to guide self-care decisions.⁵

Evidence consistently supports the benefits of regular SMBG. Studies show associations with improved glycaemic control, reduced risk of hypoglycaemic events, lower rates of microvascular complications, and enhanced overall quality of life.^{8,9} Incorporating SMBG into comprehensive diabetes management has been shown to contribute up to a 15% reduction in microvascular complications in individuals living with T2DM.¹⁰ By enabling timely treatment adjustments and reinforcing adherence to lifestyle and medication regimens, SMBG strengthens patients' engagement in their own care.⁹

Despite these advantages, adherence to SMBG varies widely across populations. Socioeconomic status, cultural norms, health system limitations, and disparities in access to monitoring tools have

significant influence on SMBG uptake.^{11,12} In Nigeria, reported SMBG prevalence ranges from 15% to 40%, with major determinants including educational level, income, insulin use, and access to healthcare services.⁶ Suboptimal practice remains pronounced in low- and middle-income settings, where financial constraints, inadequate diabetes education, and weak health system support hinder regular monitoring.^{12,13} Additional barriers include the high cost of glucometers and test strips, limited patient knowledge of proper SMBG techniques, and insufficient guidance from healthcare providers.^{14,15}

Notably, there is paucity of published data from Sokoto and the wider north-west region of Nigeria on this subject matter. This gap limits understanding of the true prevalence, patterns, and determinants of SMBG in this population, thereby underscoring the need for context-specific research to inform targeted interventions.

The study aimed to determine the prevalence and determinants of self-monitoring of blood glucose among adults with Type II Diabetes Mellitus attending the Medical Outpatient Clinic of UDUTH, Sokoto. It specifically assessed the proportion of patients who practise SMBG and the sociodemographic and clinical factors associated with its practice. The study also explored patient-reported barriers to regular SMBG

Methodology

Study site and design

This hospital-based cross-sectional study was conducted at the Medical Outpatient Clinic of Usmanu Danfodiyo University Teaching Hospital (UDUTH), Sokoto. UDUTH, located in Sokoto metropolis in northwestern Nigeria (Latitude 13.0059°N, Longitude 5.2476°E), is a major referral centre serving Sokoto State and neighbouring regions, including Kebbi, Zamfara, and parts of Niger Republic. The hospital offers specialist services in internal medicine, and its Medical Outpatient Clinic runs weekly sessions that manage an average of 80 T2DM patients per week.

Study population and sampling

The study population comprised adults aged 18 years diagnosed with T2DM using WHO criteria

and receiving follow-up care for at least six months at the Medical Outpatient Clinic of UDUTH. Eligible participants were regular clinic attendees (≥ 3 visits in the last six months) and provided informed consent. Excluded were patients with other forms of diabetes, pregnant women, and those who were acutely or critically ill. The sample size was determined using Fisher's formula for descriptive studies, based on a 15.3% prevalence of SMBG from a previous study.¹¹ The calculated minimum sample size was 199; however, to enhance precision and accommodate potential non-response, the final sample size was increased to 218 participants.

Data collection method

Data were collected using a pretested, interviewer-administered structured proforma adapted from a previous study and validated for local use. The instrument comprised sections on sociodemographic characteristics, clinical information, SMBG practices, knowledge, barriers, and attitudes toward SMBG.

A **simple random sampling technique** was employed to select participants. Each clinic day, a sampling frame was generated from the clinic attendance register listing all eligible adults with T2DM. Every eligible patient was assigned a unique number, and the lottery method was used to randomly select participants until the required daily sample was obtained. Selected patients were approached, the study procedures explained, and written informed consent obtained. Those who declined or were found ineligible were replaced by another randomly selected eligible patient. This method ensured equal selection probability and minimized sampling bias.

Trained research assistants conducted face-to-face interviews in either English or Hausa, depending on participant preference, to accommodate varying literacy levels. Each interview lasted approximately 15–20 minutes and was conducted in a private area of the clinic to maintain confidentiality and reduce response bias. Quality assurance measures included pretesting the proforma, training research assistants on interview procedures and ethics, and daily review of completed forms by the principal investigator to

ensure completeness and consistency. These measures ensured standardized data collection and enhanced the reliability and validity of the study findings.

Data Management and Analysis

Data were managed and analysed using the SPSS Statistics. Initial exploratory data checks were performed to identify and correct incomplete or erroneous entries. Quantitative variables were summarized using mean and standard deviation, while categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. Associations between categorical variables were assessed using Pearson's chi-square test or Fisher's exact test where appropriate.

Variables that showed significant associations with SMBG on bivariate analysis were entered into a multivariate binary logistic regression model to identify independent predictors of SMBG practice. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$, and confidence intervals were computed at the 95% level. Results were presented in tables accompanied by explanatory notes.

Ethical Approval and Consent to Participate

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of Usmanu Danfodiyo University Teaching Hospital, Sokoto (NHREC/UDUTH-HREC/2025/1604/V1). The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki (2013). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to enrolment, and confidentiality of participants' information was strictly maintained.

Results

Sociodemographic and Clinical Characteristics:

A total of 218 adults with T2DM participated in the study, with a mean age of 54.1 ± 10.9 years; most were female (70.6%) and married (69.7%). A substantial proportion had no formal education (40.4%), and unemployment was common (35.3%), with 41.7% earning below ₦50,000 monthly (Table 1).

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of study participants (n = 218)

Demographic variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)	30–39	23	10.6
	40–49	45	20.6
	50–59	77	35.3
	60–69	56	25.7
	70–79	13	6.0
	≥80	4	1.8
Gender	Male	64	29.4
	Female	154	70.6
Marital status	Single	22	10.1
	Married	152	69.7
	Divorced	13	6.0
	Widowed	31	14.2
Educational level	No formal education	88	40.4
	Primary	32	14.7
	Secondary	42	19.3
	Tertiary	56	25.7
Employment status	Employed	50	22.9
	Self-employed	82	37.6
	Unemployed	77	35.3
	Retired	9	4.1
Monthly income (₦)	<50,000	91	41.7
	50,000–100,000	37	17.0
	>100,000	87	39.9
	Not disclosed	3	1.4

₦ naira

Clinically, 42.2% had lived with DM for over 10 years, nearly all were on oral anti-diabetic therapy, and 28.4% used insulin in combination. Diabetes-related complications were reported by 47.7% of them, predominantly microvascular, and clinic attendance was mainly monthly or quarterly (Table2).

Table 2: Clinical characteristics of study participants (n = 218)

Clinical Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Duration of illness	<1 year	9	4.1
	1–5 years	65	29.8
	5–10 years	52	23.9
	>10 years	92	42.2
Use of insulin	Yes	62	28.4
	No	156	71.6
Use of oral antidiabetics	Yes	207	95.0
	No	11	5.0
Diabetes-related complications present	Yes	104	47.7
	No	114	52.3
Type of complications (n = 108)	Microvascular	84	77.8
	Macro vascular	18	16.7
	Both	6	5.6
Clinic attendance frequency	Weekly	2	0.9
	Monthly	83	38.1
	Quarterly	84	38.5
	Occasionally	49	22.5
Ever had Diabetes education	Yes	181	83.0
	No	33	15.1
	No response	4	1.8
Possession of glucometer	Yes	110	50.5
	No	108	49.5

Prevalence of Self-Monitoring of Blood Glucose among Study Participants

Of the 218 participants, 121 (55.5%) practiced self-monitoring of blood glucose, while 94 (43.1%) did not; 3 (1.4%) provided no response (Table 3).

Table 3: Practice of SMBG among participants (n = 218)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Practice of SMBG	Yes	121	55.5
	No	94	43.1
	No response	3	1.4
Knowledge of how to use Glucometer	Yes	110	50.5
	No	94	43.1
	No response	14	6.4

*SMBG; self-monitoring of blood glucose

Among participants who practiced SMBG, 33.1% monitored daily, 31.4% several times weekly, while 16.5% and 19.0% monitored once weekly or less, respectively (Figure I)

*SBMG; self-monitoring of blood glucose

Figure I: Frequency of self-monitoring of blood glucose (SMBG) among practicing participants (n=121).

Sociodemographic and clinical factors associated with self-monitoring of blood glucose practices.

The association between self-monitoring of blood glucose practice and sociodemographic variables is shown in table 4 with higher SMBG practice observed among males, participants with higher education, those who were employed and having higher income.

Table 4: Association between demographic variables and self-monitoring of blood Glucose

Demographic Variables	Categories	SMBG: Yes (n)	SMBG: No (n)	χ^2	df	P-value
Gender	Male	47 (73.4)	17 (26.6)	10.903	1	0.001
	Female	74 (49)	77 (51.0)			
Marital Status	Single	15 (68.2)	7 (31.8)	7.215	3	0.065
	Married	88 (59.1)	61 (40.9)			
	Divorced	7 (53.8)	6 (46.2)			
	Widowed	11 (35.5)	20 (64.5)			
Education	No formal education	23 (27.1)	62 (72.9)	61.787	3	<0.001
	Primary	18 (56.3)	14 (43.8)			
	Secondary	28 (66.7)	14 (33.3)			
	Tertiary	52 (92.9)	4 (7.1)			
Employment Status	Employed	38 (76)	12 (24.0)	57.979	3	<0.001
	Self-employed	58 (70.7)	24 (29.3)			
	Unemployed	16 (21.6)	58 (78.4)			
	Retired	9 (100)	0 (0)			
Income	<50,000	20 (22.7)	68 (77.3)	80.187	3	<0.001
	50,000–100,000	25 (67.6)	12 (32.4)			
	>100,000	76 (87.4)	11 (12.6)			
	No response	0 (0)	3 (100)			
Age Category (years)	30–39	15 (65.2)	8 (34.8)	13.593	5	0.018
	40–49	27 (60)	18 (40.0)			
	50–59	41 (53.2)	36 (46.8)			
	60–69	32 (60.4)	21 (39.6)			
	70–79	2 (15.4)	11 (84.6)			
	80+	4 (100)	0 (0)			

*p-value <0.05, SBMG; self-monitoring of blood glucose

The association between self-monitoring of blood glucose practice and clinical variables is shown in table 5 below.

Table 5: Association between clinical variables and self-monitoring of blood glucose

Clinical Variable	Categories	SMBG: Yes (n)	SMBG: No (n)	χ^2	df	p-value
Duration of Illness	<1 year	6 (66.7)	3 (33.3)	15.077	3	0.002
	1–5 years	24 (36.9)	41 (63.1)			
	>5–10 years	29 (59.2)	20 (40.8)			
	>10 years	62 (67.4)	30 (32.6)			
Insulin use	Yes	44 (71.0)	18 (29.0)	7.640	1	0.006
	No	77 (50.3)	76 (49.7)			
Oral anti-diabetic use	Yes	114 (55.9)	90 (44.1)	0.255	1	0.614
	No	7 (63.6)	4 (36.4)			
DM complications present	Yes	49 (48.5)	52 (51.5)	4.667	1	0.031
	No	72 (63.2)	42 (36.8)			
Type of complication	Microvascular	38 (45.2)	46 (54.8)	4.613	2	0.100
	Macrovascular	11 (73.3)	4 (26.7)			
	Microvascular + Macrovascular	2 (33.3)	4 (66.7)			
Clinic visit frequency	Weekly	2 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	20.391	3	<0.001
	Monthly	61 (73.5)	22 (26.5)			
	Quarterly	34 (40.5)	50 (59.5)			
	Occasionally	24 (52.2)	22 (47.8)			
Ever had Diabetes education	Yes	117 (64.6)	64 (35.4)	35.174	1	<0.001
	No	2 (6.7)	28 (93.3)			

*p-value <0.05, SBMG; self-monitoring of blood glucose, DM; diabetes mellitus,

df: degree of freedom

Table 6: Binary logistic regression analysis of SMBG in the study population (Independent predictors of SMBG in the study population)

Demographic & Clinical Variables	OR (Exp (B))	95% CI Lower	Upper	p-value
Gender	0.018	0.000	1.30	0.052
Marital status	3.261	0.90	11.82	0.072
Education	0.448	0.19	1.05	0.072
Employment status	5.756	1.33	24.90	0.020*
Income	0.050	0.005	0.52	0.011*
Duration of Illness	0.276	0.09	0.87	0.027*
Oral anti-diabetic use	0.151	0.020	1.169	0.070
Insulin use	0.062	0.00	1.11	0.060
DM complications present	0.677	0.291	1.574	0.365
Ever had Diabetes education	25.59	5.91	110.93	<0.001*

*Significant at $p < 0.05$, DM; diabetes mellitus, OR; odds ratio, CI; confidence interval

Employment, income, duration of illness, and ever had diabetes education were independent predictors of SMBG, with ever had diabetes education showing the strongest association (OR 25.59, $p < 0.001$).

Results of barriers to self-monitoring of blood glucose among study participants

Among respondents who reported barriers to SMBG, the most common were the cost of glucometers and test strips (57.7%) and lack of knowledge on how to use glucometer (48.6%), as shown in Figure 2

Figure 2: Barriers to self-monitoring of blood glucose among participants (n=111)

Discussion

Self-monitoring of blood glucose is a cornerstone of diabetes self-management, allowing individuals to track their glucose levels, adjust medications or diet, and prevent hypo- or hyperglycaemia. This study found that about half of individuals with T2DM practiced SMBG, similar to reports from Nigeria and Malaysia.^{11,12} Although this indicates increasing awareness, the uptake remains below global expectations. The American Diabetes Association (ADA) identifies SMBG as essential for diabetes self-care, especially for insulin users.¹⁶ Despite this, only a third of participants monitored their glucose daily. This highlights persistent gaps in adherence to recommended SMBG frequency.

Most participants monitored their glucose using personal glucometers, mainly during fasting periods, consistent with patterns reported in China and Ethiopia.^{17,18} Although fasting tests are perceived as more meaningful, relying solely on them may miss important postprandial fluctuations crucial for glycaemic control.⁵ Recording results through glucometer memory or notepads also raises concerns about accuracy and continuity of self-care documentation.

Gender, education, employment, age and income were significantly associated with SMBG practices. Men were more likely to practice SMBG compared to women. This finding aligns with Ojewale et al, who reported gender disparities in diabetes self-care, partly attributed to men's greater financial resources and decision-making autonomy in many African settings.¹⁹ Educational status was strongly associated with SMBG. Respondents with tertiary education had the highest prevalence of SMBG. This agrees with studies in Nigeria and Ghana, which found education to be a key enabler of diabetes self-care, as it enhances awareness, comprehension of health information, and correct interpretation of SMBG results.^{12,13,20}

Income was another strong determinant. Less than a quarter of those earning below ₦50,000 practiced SMBG compared to almost nine in ten among those earning above ₦100,000. This

underscores the role of economic capacity in affording glucometers and test strips, which remain largely out-of-pocket expenses in Nigeria.^{12,14} Employment status followed a similar pattern, with unemployed respondents least likely to practice SMBG. These findings reaffirm the link between socioeconomic advantage and access to diabetes self-management resources.⁶

Patients aged 30–59 years were more likely to monitor their glucose than those above 60 years. This trend may reflect reduced health literacy and greater dependence on caregivers among older adults, as highlighted by Pandey et al.²¹ Several clinical variables significantly influenced SMBG practice. Duration of diabetes was important, with patients living with diabetes for more than 10 years more likely to practice SMBG compared to those diagnosed within 1–5 years. This observation is consistent with Raoufi et al. and Ewunetu et al, who noted that longer disease duration often increases patients' awareness of complications and their motivation to monitor blood glucose.^{17,18}

Insulin use was also significantly associated with SMBG. Seven in ten insulin users monitored their glucose compared to fewer oral-only users. This finding reflects international guidelines, which emphasize SMBG as essential in insulin-treated patients to prevent hypoglycaemia.²² Patients with regular weekly and monthly visits demonstrated higher practice levels than those with quarterly or occasional visits. This suggests that closer follow-up provides more opportunities for reinforcement of SMBG practices, consistent with findings by other researchers.²³

Furthermore, diabetes education showed a strong positive association with SMBG. This study shows that diabetes education plays an important role in encouraging patients to adopt SMBG as part of their self-care when compared to those not educated. This is consistent with evidence from Nigeria and broader African studies,^{6,24,25} which demonstrate that structured diabetes self-management education (DSME) significantly improves SMBG adherence. Diabetes complications were associated with reduced

SMBG, suggesting that poor monitoring may contribute to complications or that complications hinder regular SMBG. This aligns with findings by Iwuala et al., who reported an association between inadequate SMBG and poor glycaemic control.¹³ Binary logistic regression showed that income, employment, duration of diabetes, and diabetes education were independent predictors of SMBG practice. Income remained a strong determinant, highlighting affordability challenges previously noted in studies in Nigeria.^{12,13} A longer duration of diabetes also predicted SMBG, supporting evidence that extended disease experience promotes self-monitoring.¹⁷ Diabetes education emerged as the strongest determinant, highlighting its pivotal role. This finding aligns with studies from Mali and Ethiopia, where diabetes self-management education significantly improved self-monitoring of blood glucose and glycaemic outcomes.^{25,26} The loss of statistical significance for gender, marital status, and insulin use after adjustment suggests their effects may operate through socioeconomic or educational pathways.

The major barriers to SMBG were the cost of glucometers and test strips and inadequate knowledge on how to use glucometer. The prominence of financial constraints mirrors earlier Nigerian findings, where out-of-pocket payment remains the leading obstacle to regular SMBG,^{6,12} especially in settings with limited insurance coverage.¹³ This contrasts with high-income countries where subsidization improves access.⁹ Knowledge-related challenges were also common and align with reports that inadequate training on SMBG techniques hinders effective utilization.^{14,23} Other less frequently cited barriers such as inconvenience, pain, forgetfulness, and low motivation are consistent with previous studies highlighting the need for behavioural support in addition to affordability and education.^{6,15} Key limitations of this study include the cross-sectional design, which precludes causal inference; the hospital-based single-site sample, which limits generalizability; and reliance on self-reported data, introducing potential recall and social desirability bias.

Conclusion

This study shows that the prevalence of SMBG among adults with T2DM in Sokoto is moderately high, but practices remain irregular and suboptimal. Socioeconomic factors, clinical experience, and structured diabetes education were identified as predictors of SMBG practice. Cost and lack of knowledge were identified as significant barriers to adoption of the practice. These findings highlight the need for multifaceted interventions addressing financial, educational, and systemic challenges to enhance SMBG uptake and improve DM outcomes in Sokoto, Nigeria. Future research should examine the long-term effects of SMBG on glycaemic control in Nigeria, especially the impact of subsidizing glucometers and test strips. Qualitative studies are also needed to better understand psychosocial and cultural barriers, which can guide the development of context-specific strategies to improve adherence.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and publication of this manuscript.

Authors' Contributions

Abdullahi I.A. conceptualized and designed the study, supervised data collection, performed data analysis, and drafted the manuscript. Abdullahi F. and Abdullahi B.U contributed to data collection and initial manuscript review. Muhammad A., Abdullahi M.A., and assisted with data interpretation, literature review. Polycarp D.M. did critical revision of the manuscript for intellectual content. All authors read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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